

Supporting under-represented groups, addressing non-inclusive behaviour, and addressing gender bias in plant sciences

Report from CSIRO-Australian National University Women in Crop Science coffee

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As part of the recent Global Women in Crop Science coffee events held around the world (<https://womenincropscience.org/global-coffee-morning/>) an in person event was held at CSIRO, Canberra on Monday 22nd August with virtual attendees and a satellite event at CSIRO, Brisbane. The event was hosted by Jessica Hyles, Fernanda Dreccer and Maja Arsic (CSIRO), Caitlin Byrt (Australian National University). The event had 40 in-person attendees, plus 20 online participants. The event included an introductory short talk by Jen Taylor (CSIRO Acting Business Unit Director), Jess Hyles (CSIRO Group Leader, Cotton Biotechnology) and a presentation by Alison Bentley (CIMMYT Global Wheat Program). This was followed by a networking morning tea with discussions and interactions supported by the CSIRO Inclusion and Diversity Initiative. This report summarizes the background and outcomes of the discussion topics.

Women in Crop Science event in Canberra with (top left) CSIRO Acting Business Unit Director Jen Taylor, CSIRO Group Leader, Cotton Biotechnology Jessica Hyles and CIMMYT Global Wheat Program Director Alison Bentley; (top right) co-host Caitlin Byrt (Australian National University); discussions and interactions during the networking morning tea supported by the CSIRO GDI team

Background areas covered

- A recent analysis by Caitlin Byrt (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7084163>) highlights the fact that in the last decade, three times more male mid-career plant science researchers in Australia have been awarded fellowships compared to females at the same career stage. Overall, the report highlights the need for systems to be in place to address biases and disadvantages to female scientists in decisions regarding funding, hiring, promotion and tenure. This was used to set the context for topic three which was discussed in small groups.
- Many organizations in Australia, including CSIRO, have made great progress in promoting and enhancing diversity. Given this progress it would be useful to share the successes (and the process for achieving them e.g., policies, initiatives) widely so that others can take the learnings from these successes forward in their organizations (particularly recognizing that some countries are not as advanced in their work on gender diversity and inclusion (GDI)).

Topics discussed and summary of ideas captured

During the morning tea, three topics were discussed by participants using flip charts to capture a range of ideas.

1. How can we support career development for under-represented groups?

This discussion topic identified a range of opportunities to provide greater support, which are broadly grouped into recommendations for HR departments, networking and awareness raising, and training.

HR recommendations

- When advertising education/career opportunities to students (of all ages), make sure it is inclusive and doesn't support stereotypes or any bias.
- Through HR – provide feedback and formalize support for ensuring equality for under-represented groups.
- Put in place reviews and/or processes that allow for identification of less obvious candidates: expand the criteria with which different HR processes are conducted and the assessment of individuals against these criteria.
- Consider different ways to measure success in annual reviews, promotions etc. Linking to identification of more diverse candidates in recruitment. Strengthen supervisor engagement in the promotion process, including through provision of training. Ensure that top-down support exists from supervisors, and management positions. Provide supervisors with tools/knowledge to recognize talent early and mechanisms to encourage it.
- Ensure managers/senior leadership are actively engaged with and listening to members of underrepresented communities to ensure their issues and suggestions are being accurately understood, and the proposed actions are also reflective of what the community is comfortable with rather than making assumptions. Develop/provide a mechanism for this.
- Target removal of self-selection against women, potentially offering this as a component of training.
- Ensure that there is a system or process in place to capture the difference in opportunity awarded to employees working full vs part time. This is essential to ensure that progress and awards adequately reflect this.

Networking & raising awareness

- Organize regular events to raise awareness and facilitate people from all backgrounds making connections
- Emphasize existing diverse role models, or actively discuss and recognize if they don't exist
- Put in place systems or events that allow senior staff to not only mentor but advocate for junior colleagues to senior staff/leadership.
- Forming underrepresented groups like WICS – allows similar group of people to share, encourage and discuss strategies and ideas as a collective.
- Share case studies and examples.

Training

- Beware of work/training overload and excluding people based on their ability to attend (e.g., accounting for childcare and other responsibilities).
- Teach skills in self-advocacy as well as targeted training, including soft-skills training.
- Provide training in addition to existing unconscious bias training to highlight that underrepresented communities will have diverse opinions, needs and preferences within themselves which should also be respected.

2. How do we collectively address non-inclusive behaviours?

This discussion area highlighted a range of recommendations that could be broadly grouped into organizational and operational actions.

Organisational

- Organisational values should clearly include 'gender-balance'.
- Regularly reward and celebrate examples of behaviours we want to see to reinforce positive behaviours aligned to organizational values.
- Reward-punishment system, so people are aware of repercussions of non-inclusive behaviour
- Set an organizational standard for abstaining from presenting or sponsoring conferences which are non-inclusive. Raise awareness with conference committees when conferences are non-inclusive. Demand change!
- Create anonymous feedback channels in organisations to report behaviours or provide suggestions about address non-inclusive behaviours
- Ensure bias in next generation is addressed – create inclusive student/intern programs
- Ensure diversity and inclusion training for all group leaders/PIs.

Operational

- "Call-out" non-inclusive behaviours, and "Just say it". That will encourage others to do so too.
- Create committees like the CALD (culturally and linguistically diverse) team at CSIRO, with a focus on Gender Diversity to recommend operational changes.
- Embed inclusivity in operational processes (top-down) to support the upholding of organisational values
- Avoid age restrictions in career awards/advancements for women
- If a female colleague's valid suggestion is being ignored, repeat what she said until it is acknowledged.
- If an idea is picked up by a male colleague as their own, bring it back to how much you liked the original idea as stated by your female colleague
- If a female colleague's idea is being overly criticized, support your colleague by reframing the idea to address some of the criticism

- If verbal contributions are being cut off, “butt in” by interrupting and saying “hang on, I’d really like to hear more first about what XX was saying”, and speak to managers after the meeting to ask for support or to deal with the behaviour in future meetings
- Propose a “blind” system – colleagues can email in or drop suggestions into a hat anonymously. All ideas can then be discussed in the meeting
- Ensure authorship is discussed very early on in the process, ideally before writing begins for all scientific and outreach publications.
- Acknowledge all who have contributed without bias (e.g., technicians deserve authorship credit, etc.).

3. How do we address gender bias in awards and funding?

The recent analysis conducted by Caitlin Byrt identified large disparity in the awarding of mid-career fellowships between male and female candidates. This topic identified several general recommendations for improving the inclusivity and transparency of the process for awards and funding that could be broadly grouped into bottom-up and top-down actions.

Bottom-up actions

- Forward opportunities to someone you think is eligible; encourage others to apply
- Prioritize networking and making new connections at conferences and events: get to know the community and range of skills that are available within the talent pool.
- Continue to arrange and attend meetings such as Coffee Mornings to celebrate good news, opportunities coming up.

Top-down actions

- Ensure award and funding panels are gender balanced and culturally diverse, with a chair that has undertaken inclusion & diversity training. Use resources, such as the Women in Crop Science Directory (<https://womenincropscience.org/directory/>) to diversify panel membership. Panel membership should also be changed regularly to avoid accumulation of biases.
- Introduce mandatory 50/50 gender balance for awards/grants. This has already been successfully implemented by the National Health and Medical Research Council in Australia and cross-learning is encouraged.
- De-identify gender/name/organisation information in applications to remove bias.
- Blind interview processes for gender, race, age as much as possible (e.g., initial CVs should remove names and photos)
- Consider the possibility to advertise some positions as female only (anecdote – for a university Associate Professor position, almost no female candidates applied for the role when it was open to all genders. When they advertised as women-only, they were overwhelmed with applications as this appeared to remove some of the initial bias more women tend to have by underestimating their abilities to perform in a role).
- Make hiring and retention statistics more transparent within organizations and grants.